

Synthesis, Characterisation and Antibacterial Activities of some New Schiff Base Compounds

SONAL SHAH, RAJEEV VYAS and R. H. MEHTA*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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Naturally occurring coumarins have easy acceptability in the biological systems¹. Several coumarin derivatives possess various biological activities². On the other hand, the presence of azomethine linkage in the compound is found to exhibit antibacterial activity³. It was, therefore, thought of interest to synthesise potent antibacterial agent by incorporating azomethine linkage in the various 8-hydroxy-, 8-methoxy- and 7-hydroxycoumarins and to screen them for their antibacterial activity.

characteristic absorption bands at 3 400 (NH) except 3a–c, 1 730–1 705 (lactonic C=O) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C ring stretch). Elemental analyses corroborated with their molecular formula.

All the Schiff bases are sharp melting solid (Table 1). However some ¹H pmr results are interesting, e.g. 1d (*p*-methyl and methoxy protons of C-8 position of coumarin ring), 4a (*m*-methoxy protons and methyl protons of C-8-C-CH₃) and 4c (methyl protons of C-8-C-CH₃) showed two peaks in each case for methyl and methoxy protons partially resolved (difference ranging from δ 0.01 to 0.05). This provide strong evidence that these compounds are of single stereoisomeric form but on solution, isomerisation⁴ occurs too rapidly.

Antibacterial activity: Some representative compounds from each series (1a, i, j; 2e, i, j, k; 3b, d, 4e) were screened for antibacterial activity using cup-plate method⁵ at 100 and 500 ppm concentrations against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. albus* and *B. subtilis*. Antibacterial activity has not been observed with naturally occurring simple 8-hydroxy- and 8-methoxycoumarins⁶. At 500 ppm concentration level the following compounds showed significant activity (zone of inhibition, mm, in parenthesis): 1a (15–26 mm against all organisms), 1j (17–28 against *E. coli*, *S. albus* and *B. subtilis*), 2j and 2k (14 and 28 against *S. aureus* and *S. albus* respectively), 3b (23 and 25 against *E. coli* and *S. albus*), 3d (18 and 24 against *E. coli* and *S. albus*) and 4e (17 against *E. coli*). From the results, it seems that azomethine linkage is perhaps an essential structural requirement for such activity.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of all the compounds exhibited

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1—4

Compd. no.	R	M.p.* °C
1a	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	233 ^a
b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	242 ^a
c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	275 ^a
d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	257 ^a
e	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	293 ^a
f	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	214 ^a
g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	304 ^a
h	<i>o</i> -Cl	225 ^a
i	<i>p</i> -Cl	257 ^a
j	<i>m</i> -Br	222 ^a
k	<i>p</i> -OH	285 ^a
l	<i>p</i> -NH ₂	278 ^a
m	Thiosemicarbazone	275 ^a
n	Semicarbazone	300 ^b
2a	CH ₃	266 ^a
b	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	235 ^c
c	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	177 ^d
d	2,3-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	234 ^a
e	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	210 ^a
f	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	225 ^a
g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	272 ^a
h	<i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄	228 ^e
i	<i>p</i> -CH-C ₆ H ₄	278 ^a
j	2-OH,5-Br-C ₆ H ₃	213 ^a
k	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	285 ^a
l	Piperonal	242 ^e
3a	C ₆ H ₅	209 ^c
b	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	218 ^f
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	232 ^e
d	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -CONH	235 ^f
4a	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	235 ^a
b	<i>m</i> -Br	284 ^a
c	<i>p</i> -Cl	283 ^a
d	<i>p</i> -OH	300 ^a
e	<i>p</i> -NH ₂	277 ^a
1d	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 1 700 cm ⁻¹ ; δ 2.1 (3H, s, ArCH ₃), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.5 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C-3-H), 8.4 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C-4-H), 7-7.6 (m, ArH and =CH); <i>m/z</i> 336 (<i>M</i> ⁺ 10), 217 (8), 119 (base peak 100), 91 (35), 65 (12); <i>1g</i> $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400, 1 710, 1 690 cm ⁻¹ ; δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.52 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, C-3-H), 8.1 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, C-4-H), 7-7.9 (m, br, ArH and =CH); <i>2l</i> $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400, 1 730 cm ⁻¹ ; δ 3.75 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.62 (2H, s, CH ₂ N), 5.7 (2H, s, OCH ₂ O), 6.5 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C-3-H), 7.9 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C-4-H) 6.5-7.65 (m, ArH and =CH); <i>3a</i> $\nu_{\max}$ 1 720 cm ⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl ₃) 6.4 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C-3-H), 7.55 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C-4-H), 6.9-7.4 (m, ArH), 8.55 (1H, s, =CH); <i>m/z</i> 265 (<i>M</i> ⁺ 10), 237 (42), 180 (20), 77 (45); <i>4a</i> $\nu_{\max}$ 3 350, 1 730 cm ⁻¹ ; δ 2.2 (3H, s, C-4, CH ₃), 2.9 (3H, s, C-8, =C-CH ₃), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.2 (1H, s, C-3-H), 7-7.8 (m, ArH); <i>m/z</i> 366 (<i>M</i> ⁺ 20), 135 (base peak 100), 107 (25), 77 (22); <i>4c</i> $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400, 1 730 1 785 cm ⁻¹ ; δ 2.3 (3H, s, C-4, CH ₃), 2.9 (3H, s, C-8, C=CH ₃), 6.2 (1H, s, C-3-H), 7.1-7.8, (m, br, ArH).	

*Solvent for crystallisation: ^aDMF+water, ^bDMF, ^cEtOH, ^dEtOH+C₆H₆, ^eEtOH+DMF, ^fEtOH+water

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries using a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were performed on a Coleman instrument. It spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CF₃-COOH) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as the internal standard. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

8-Methoxy-5-formylcoumarin: A mixture of 8-methoxy-5-chloromethylcoumarin⁷ (1.0 g) and hexamine (5.0 g) in chloroform (20–25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 h. The separated product was refluxed in acetic acid (20% ; 50 ml) on a steam-bath for 4 h. Formyl derivative separated during the reaction, was crystallised from 1 : 1 acetic acid as light yellow needles (75–80%), m.p. 218° (Found: C, 64.59; H, 3.61. C₁₁H₈O₄ calcd. for C, 64.71; H, 3.92%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 710–1 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CF₃COOH) 3.8 (3H, s, C-8-OCH₃), 6.5 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C-3-H), 7.1 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C-6 or C-7-H), 7.7 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C-6 or C-7-H), 9.05 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C-4-H) and 9.6 (1H, s, C-5-CHO).

N-(8-Methoxy-5-coumarilidene)-substituted benzoic acid hydrazones (1a–n): A mixture of 8-methoxy-5-formylcoumarin (0.01 mol) and various substituted acid hydrazides (0.01 mol) in alcohol (50 ml) with a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a sand-bath for 0.5 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from appropriate solvents (yield 73–86%).

8-Methoxy-5-anilinomethyl (o-(N-substituted benzylidene)-coumarin (2a–l): A mixture of 8-methoxy-5-(*o*-amino)-anilinomethylcoumarin⁸ (0.01 mol) and various aldehydes (0.01 mol) in absolute alcohol was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. Alcohol was (50 ml) then removed by vacuum distillation and the resulting solid was crystallised from appropriate solvents (yield 57–80%).

7-(Substituted-phenyliminomethyl)-8-hydroxycoumarins (3a–d): A mixture of 8-hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin⁹ (0.01 mol) and various substituted arylamines and acid hydrazides alcohol (50 ml) with a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The solid separated on cooling was crystallised from appropriate solvents (yield 75–85%).

(7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-yl)ethylidene-(substituted)benzoic acid hydrazide (4a–e): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-5-methylcoumarin¹⁰ (0.01 mol) and various substituted acid hydrazides (0.01 mol) in alcohol (50 ml) with a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on sand-bath for 1 h. The separated solids were crystallised from appropriate solvents (yield 65–81%).

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References

1. P. K. BOSE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 35, 367; J. M. CASSADY, N. OJIMA, C. J. CHANG and J. L. McLOUGHLIN, *Nat. Prod.*, 1979, 42, 274; R. A. FINNEGAN, K. E. MERKEL and N. BACK, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1972, 61, 1599.

2. A. K. SENGUPTA, S. SEN and V. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, 66, 710; Y. D. REDDY and V. V. SOMAYAYULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 599.
3. F. D. POPP, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1566; J. SENGUPTA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 33; D. R. SHRIDHAR, L. C. VISHWAKARMA and A. K. S. B. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 48.
4. D. Y. CURTIN and J. W. HAUSSE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3974.
5. F. CAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 126.
6. L. JURD, J. CORSE, A. D. KING, JR., H. BAYNE and K. HIHARA, *Photochemistry*, 1971, 10, 2971.
7. Y. K. SATO, N. T. YUTAKA, O. TAKESHI, S. KUMKURA, K. NAKAYAMA, H. KOIKI and N. TAKAGI, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1972, 20, 905 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 77, 101337).
8. S. SHAH and R. H. MEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, 66, 802.
9. R. H. MEHTA and S. SETHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 384.
10. A. RUSSEL and J. R. FRYE, *Org. Synth.*, 1955, 3, 281.